

Investigation of reactive species formation in surface dielectric barrier discharge with liquid electrodes

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This study focuses on the characterization and quantification of reactive species produced by cold plasma generated using liquid electrodes in a surface dielectric barrier discharge system. By varying experimental conditions, the production of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species in both gas and liquid phases was systematically analysed. Several analytical techniques were employed to assess the chemical composition of the plasma-treated medium.

1 General

The typical surface dielectric barrier discharge (SDBD) systems, produce plasma along a thin dielectric layer and are not capable of direct interaction with liquids. This limitation restricts the formation of short-lived, highly reactive species, such as hydroxyl ($\cdot\text{OH}$) and oxide ($\cdot\text{O}$) radicals and their transport to liquids. To overcome this challenge, we use a liquid electrode SDBD system, where plasma is ignited directly from the liquid surface [1,2]. This approach significantly enhances plasma-liquid interactions, making the system more versatile for applications such as water activation, material surface treatment, and biomedical sterilization.

Liquids that are plasma-treated and contain a mixture of various reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (RONS) are typically referred to as plasma-activated liquids (PAL). Key reactive species such as $\cdot\text{OH}$, O_3 , NO , NO_2 , and H_2O_2 play crucial roles in plasma-driven surface modifications and decontamination processes [3,4]. The interaction of these species with target surfaces during plasma treatment significantly influences the reaction pathways and outcomes.

This study presents an investigation of the electrical discharge properties of a cold plasma that is created using liquid electrodes. The chemical species that are created during the discharge and subsequently transferred into the liquid are systematically characterized and quantified.

To characterize the reactive species formed in the gas phase, Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was used to quantify gas-phase species, such as NO , NO_2 , N_2O , and O_3 . The concentration of nitrogen-containing species showed fluctuations with increased discharge power, peaking at approximately 50 ppm. Meanwhile, O_3

concentrations reached up to 150 ppm, varying based on reactor type and discharge power.

In addition, the analysis of these species, as well as the detailed composition of the plasma were studied by using mass spectroscopy. The spatial evolution of O_3 within the liquid phase was further analyzed using in-situ UV-VIS spectroscopy.

In parallel, absorption spectroscopy was employed to quantify key plasma-induced species in the plasma-treated liquid, with concentrations measured in the mM range.

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